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Exploring Stakeholder Networks in Irregular Migration: A Visualization of Horizontal and Vertical Cooperation Frameworks

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Summary

This work provides a comparative analysis and visualization of cooperation frameworks along both horizontal and vertical axes of policymaking in the field of irregular migration. The objective was to map and illustrate stakeholder types, ties and areas of cooperation across various governance levels, including the EU, national, provincial, and local contexts. Social network analysis was chosen for the systematic collection, evaluation and visualization of data. This visual and analytical representation was further enriched by a comparative examination of how these cooperation frameworks are interconnected with data usage, data production, and governance structures, drawing on complementary literature and research findings from the MIrreM project.

The study's findings provide initial insights into stakeholders' vertical and horizontal cooperation within and across different sectors in policy development and implementation, service provision, and knowledge production. The analysis illustrates both the collaborative nature and structural tensions within and between sectors, highlighting the patterns of interaction and the power asymmetries that shape these relationships. Key findings illustrate that stakeholder cooperation in policy development and implementation in the field of irregular migration relies heavily on intrasectoral collaboration within public administration and government, with strong reciprocal relations between academia/research, NGOs/media, and government. However, tensions emerge in funding-related relations, creating information gaps and conflicting objectives, especially within public administration's vertical relations. In service provision, the findings highlight the importance of horizontal and intrasectoral cooperations, and the relevance of close cooperations between NGOs and public administration, although barriers in information exchange persist. Finally, the knowledge production network shows strong vertical connections, likely influenced by Horizon Europe funding related to irregular migration, which facilitates intensive cooperation across governance levels.

Considering the limitations of this work, particular attention should be paid to its potential value as a starting point for future research to deepen the understanding of cooperation dynamics and their long-term implications. We argue that social network analysis offers valuable insights into stakeholder cooperation patterns in irregular migration. Future research could expand network analysis in the field of irregular migration to capture whole-network interactions, revealing power dynamics and cooperation intensity across governance levels. Investigating key actors' roles in decision-making and examining gaps in stakeholder relations could enhance understanding of policy development and implementation, service provision and knowledge production in the field of irregular migration.

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THE MIRREM PROJECT

MIRreM examines estimates and statistical indicators on the irregular migrant population in Europe as well as related policies, including the regularisation of migrants in irregular situations.

MIRreM analyses policies defining migrant irregularity, stakeholders' data needs and usage, and assesses existing estimates and statistical indicators on irregular migration in the countries under study and at the EU level. Using several coordinated pilots, the project develops new and innovative methods for measuring irregular migration and explores if and how these instruments can be applied in other socio-economic or institutional contexts. Based on a broad mapping of regularisation practices in the EU as well as detailed case studies, MIRreM will develop 'regularisation scenarios' to better understand conditions under which regularisation should be considered as a policy option. Together with expert groups that will be set up on irregular migration data and regularisation, respectively, the project will synthesise findings into a Handbook on data on irregular migration and a Handbook on pathways out of irregularity. The project's research covers 20 countries, including 12 EU countries and the United Kingdom.

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Stakeholder Networks; Irregular Migration; Vertical and Horizontal Relations

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1. INTRODUCTION

Irregular migration is a highly politicized topic with a high level of publicity, media attention and societal interest. Stakeholders involved in public administration, civil society organizations, and research operate within a complex environment where actors across various governance levels pursue both common and conflicting objectives. Furthermore, actual policies frequently differ from official statements, and the actions of various actors, including public authorities and civil servants, often deviate from formal rules and public declarations (Ambrosini, 2016). Practical challenges, scope for action and different strategies in implementation are evident at different governance levels, especially in the regions, which on the one hand have to comply with national policies and legal frameworks, but also have to find ways to fulfil their obligations towards the population and manage the provision of services to irregular migrants (Cherti et al., 2024). Tensions in the relationship between European local authorities and national governments arise in different areas and show, among other things, how local and national policy responses diverge, with local authorities focusing on the socio-economic and individual impacts of exclusion, while national governments prioritise immigration control. These tensions shape multi-level governance (Spencer, 2018). They are also part of the relationships between different actors in the field of irregular migration, their cooperation, exchange and the outcomes of collaborative work.

This study aims to elucidate the complexities of stakeholder cooperation in the field of irregular migration by systematically assessing and analysing the types of stakeholders, their relations, and the subjects of their cooperation across multiple governance levels—including EU, national, provincial, and local contexts. The results of this work are also intended to complement and extend the current research findings of the MIRreM project. The findings should contribute to a more in-depth understanding of the relevance of the characteristics of stakeholder cooperations in certain areas, such as the exchange of data and information on irregular migration (Slootjes & Sohst, 2024); or the development and implementation of policies at different governance levels (Cherti et al., 2024), as well as the role of concrete national (legal) frameworks on the (cooperation) work of stakeholders in this dynamic field (Hendow et al., 2024).

Using a social network analysis approach, this study visualizes stakeholder cooperation frameworks along both horizontal and vertical axes of policymaking. This analysis explores (1) primary stakeholder types and their cooperation across and within governance levels, (2) the extent and limitations of intersectoral and intrasectoral exchange, (3) the frequency of

information exchange, and (4) the direction of cooperation (Chapter 3). To provide a deeper understanding of stakeholder cooperation, these findings are complemented by relevant literature and empirical research (Chapter 4).

The study acknowledges its methodological and practical limitations (Chapter 2), which affect the validity of its findings and the achievement of its objectives. Nevertheless, by integrating complementary sources and utilizing social network analysis, the study offers valuable insights into stakeholder cooperation and identifies open research questions for future exploration. This comprehensive approach aims to advance the understanding of how stakeholder networks shape migration governance and highlight the potential of network analysis as a tool for future research in this complex and evolving field.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 NETWORK ANALYSIS: THE METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH, TERMS, DEFINITIONS AND LIMITATIONS

The MirreM Stakeholder Network questionnaire was developed to identify the collaborations between people working in different institutions (e.g. public administration, NGOs, universities, etc.) and areas (e.g. policy development and implementation, service provision, knowledge production, etc.) dealing with irregular migration and irregular migrants. The aim was to gain an insight into whether the relationships between stakeholders from different sectors as well as within sectors take place on a vertical and horizontal level, how intensive these relationships are and from whom these relationships originate or whether they are reciprocal relationships. On this basis, the instrument of network analysis was chosen as the methodological approach.

The MIRreM stakeholder network survey was conducted using an online questionnaire, designed for an ego-centred network analysis. Ego-centred network analyses and methods focus on the individual (ego) – in this case the individual as a representative of an institution - his or her attributes and the „neighbourhood“ of ego. Ego-centered networks allow an insight into the general structure of a complete network and can offer a differentiated set of categories that are needed to study and visualise social networks¹. The composition of the stakeholders and the heterogeneity or homogeneity of the network is of particular importance for the objectives and questions of this study. The network survey addressed typical categories of network analysis, including nodes – also termed actors or alters – and the relations between the actors. Based on a general definition, networks can be defined as “[...] a way of thinking about social systems that focus our attention on the relationships among the entities that make up the system, which we call actors or nodes” (Borgatti et al., 2018: 1f.). The nodes/actors and the relationships (social ties) between them have characteristics, also called as attributes. Depending on the research focus chosen, nodes/actors can be individuals, institutions, organisations, etc. (Borgatti et al., 2018).

The questionnaire recorded the stakeholder types of the cooperation partners and the governance level to which they are assigned. The composition gives information about characteristic attributes (Marin & Wellman, 2011), for example, the proportion of governmental and academic professionals in a network. Homogeneity labels the number of

¹ It is necessary to be aware that the term “network” is a virtual term: The people who are network members and the composition of a network is always a consequence of the definition chosen (Hollstein, 2006). Furthermore, the data collection methods and data analysis depend on the form of network study chosen.

nodes with similar characteristics, such as the (primary) work area (academic sector; NGO/faith-based organisations; media; and public administration/government) and the governance level (local, provincial, national, and supranational). Individual level variables support the identification of the differences and similarities between the network respondents and, in a limited form (stakeholder type and governance level), of the alters named, and the construction of groups for comparison. The comparison of attributes of network actors allows conclusions about relationships that occur based on certain attributes. Such selection processes can be based on different criteria, such as similarities of the network actors. Borgatti et al. elaborate that “similarities” might not be a social tie but can be methodologically treated in the same way. Similarities can be reason for, but also an outcome of ties (Borgatti et al., 2018). Such selection parameters are, furthermore, interesting for conclusions about inclusion and exclusion mechanisms in (data, information) exchange systems. Regarding the specific focus of this deliverable on stakeholder networks in the field of irregular migration, every personal network represents characteristics that are partly based on the affiliation to different groups that have a collective framework and shared ascriptions of meanings and, furthermore, determine the condition of participation. The affiliation of the individual to different groups is also demonstrated by the possible variety of relations that might be interlinked with one actor. Alters might be contact points for different concerns and in a varying context. Veronika Tacke (Tacke, 2000) defines such alters as a polycontextual address. Therefore, alteri might be addressed for several purposes, for example, ego might ask an employee of the Ministry of Interior on data availability or policies and works with this person in a (governmental) funded project. Multiplex matrixes can illustrate complex sets of relationships that have a variety of differing characteristics and also exchange in different ways simultaneously (Marin & Wellman, 2011). The relation between a stakeholder in governmental administration and an employee of an NGO in the field of irregular migration, for example, might include the flow of money, knowledge and data.

“Flows” are the outcomes of interactions; in addition, “[...] interactions form the medium that enables things to flow. Flows may be intangibles, such as knowledge/ information exchange, attitudes, norms, and so on, that are passed from person to person. They can also consist of physical resources such as money or goods.” (Borgatti et al., 2018, p. 4f.) Repeating relational events can be signs of an underlying “relational state”: a stable continuing relationship (Borgatti et al., 2018), which were assessed in the network survey by questions about the intensity of the cooperation.

This differentiation is, furthermore, important for the assumptions of the survey participants about the reciprocity of the exchange. Focusing on one “dyad” – the relation between two network actors – there are three options: there is no tie, one single tie or ties in both directions (Hanneman & Riddle, 2011a). In egocentric network analysis, the confirmation of the alters named by ego is missing. This information was also supplemented in the MIRreM stakeholder network survey by the survey respondents' assessment of who is the main initiator of the cooperation. Certain asymmetric relations accompany systemic constructed reciprocal roles, such as funding providers and funding recipients, “owner” of data and recipient of data (Borgatti et al. 2013:5). “Relational events” have a discrete status and are time-bound; inside this category, there can be further differentiation between “interactions”

and “flows.” According to Borgatti et al. (2018), the exchange of data would be already an interaction and hence a “relational event.”²

The network graphs provided in this work shall support the understanding of network structures, the different types of stakeholders in the field of irregular migration and their relations. Hanneman and Riddle (2011) point to the benefits of using graphs, for example, to identify in what ways attributes (of the actors) and behaviours are influenced by his or her direct relations, and if and how conditions might be changed by actors. Furthermore, the individual’s networks can be compared and deliver information about the similarities and differences of actors and the impact on their social networks (Hanneman & Riddle, 2011b). Exemplarily, the comparison of the different graphs of personal networks was of relevance for the identification of the differences and similarities of social networks of stakeholders in the field of irregular migration who belong to a governmental institution and those who do not.

Further key terms from the questionnaire and from the network analysis are explained below. Some definitions were specifically adapted to the field of research.

Cooperation: The term ‘co-operation’, as explained in the questionnaire, refers to regular contact, in terms of data/information exchange, consultation, or direct collaboration with other stakeholders.

Vertical cooperations: Vertical cooperations refer to cooperations across different governance levels.

Horizontal cooperations: Horizontal cooperations describe cooperations within one governance level.

Intersectoral cooperations: Cooperations between different stakeholder types

Intrasectoral cooperations: Co-operation between two members of the same stakeholder type

2.2 THE NETWORK SURVEY

Development of the network survey

The MIrreM Network Survey: *Interactions between stakeholders working on irregular migration* has been developed jointly by the University for Continuing Education Krems (UWK) and the International Centre for Policy Making (ICMPD) project team. The development process focused on the following points:

- The formulation of questions and answer options regarding the feasibility of network analysis and the visualisation of cooperation frameworks along both horizontal and

² A further relevant category is “**Relational roles,**” such as to be “the mother/father/sister, etc. of...” (kinship) or the “friend/colleague/student, etc. of...” also might have implications for reciprocity and symmetry of ties; but were not assessed by the MirreM stakeholders network survey.

vertical axes in the work areas policy making, service provision and knowledge production.

- Linking the results of the analysis with further research findings of the MIRreM project.
- Alignment with the previous MIRreM survey (the MIRreM Stakeholder Mapping) and the terminology used therein.
- A review of the comprehensibility of the terms used from the perspective of the survey participants and considering possible different understandings of the terms.
- The feasibility of the questionnaire in the chosen technical tool, lime survey.

The MIRreM network survey was designed in such a way that the **stakeholder types** were defined according to their sectors of work 1) public administration or government; 2) academia, research centre or think tank; 3) NGO, grassroots or faith-based organisations; and 4) media. In addition, their main **areas of work** around irregular migration were queried, categorised as: i.) policy development, policy implementation and advocacy; ii.) service provision; iii.) knowledge production and knowledge transfer; and iv.) others (partly shortened in the following chapters to facilitate the readability). Further in-depth questions focussed on cooperation networks used for each area of work selected by the respondent. The term cooperation was defined broadly, referring to *regular contact, data/information exchange, consultation, or direct collaboration with other stakeholders*. Assessed attributes of the network partners include the stakeholder type and governance level.

Access to the network survey

In order to make the network survey as easily accessible as possible and to reduce potential barriers, it was translated from English into four additional languages (German, Italian, French and Spanish) with the support of the MIRreM project partners.

The survey could be initiated directly from the MIRreM website, via a link (e.g. embedded in emails) or via a QR code on various technical devices.

Dissemination

The MIRreM network survey was disseminated through the channels and networks already established during the project, such as the MIRreM newsletter, various social media channels ([Twitter/X](#) and [LinkedIn](#)), the MIRreM stakeholder database, the networks and contacts of the MIRreM project partners (e.g. contacts established during the intensive research work in the first year of the project), as well as the MIRreM sister projects.

Despite these extensive dissemination measures, the deadline for closing the survey needed to be extended several times. Although the scope of the questions and wording were deliberately kept to a minimum in order to save as much time as possible, many people did not complete the questionnaire in full and ultimately could not be included in the evaluation (drop-out rate of approx. 40%). In the end, further measures were taken, such as that stakeholders were researched and contacted by telephone and e-mail and asked to participate in the MIRreM network survey. Furthermore, the MIRreM project partners were

asked to contact stakeholders of their networks per personalised emails. In the end, almost 80 complete questionnaires were received.

The following figure illustrates the process using a timeline, starting with the questionnaire development phase and ending with the submission of the deliverable.

Figure 1: MIRreM stakeholder network survey: Process illustration.

2.3 LIMITATIONS

The chosen ego-centred network approach has certain limitations. Due to the high time expenditure for whole network studies it was not possible to record the network as a whole; instead, the stakeholders and relationships were recorded on the basis of the survey respondent (ego) and only in relation to their assessments of the other network stakeholders and their relationships with them (ego-centred network analyses), while whole network studies examine the relations of a predefined set of actors who are all questioned about their ties (Borgatti et al., 2018). In this work all further information about alter–alter relations (relations between the cooperation partners named by the survey respondents) are missing, i.e. a whole network structure can be only captured by including all actors in the data assessment and questioning them about their relations inside the network. This is the prerequisite for assessing different views on relations and mapping the relationships between all actors in the network; whereas in an ego network analysis, the alteri named by ego are not additionally asked about their relationships. Hanneman and Riddle (2005) state that such approaches are not “real network data”. Thus, the data of whole network studies include the data about the personal/egocentric network of each actor (Marsden et al., 2011). Even if limitations in the validity of the study results must therefore be taken into account, the methodological instruments of network analysis support the comparability of data due to standardization and can improve the understanding of the cooperation, exchanges and relations (Hollstein, 2006).

Further limitations must be considered in terms of challenges in data collection and, as an outcome, the final available database.

The original aim was to make use of different survey waves that are combined: The research approach was structured into three distinct survey phases, each designed to minimize the time and effort for survey respondents while addressing specific research objectives. The initial survey primarily aimed to register interested stakeholders by collecting personal information, serving multiple purposes: as a source for qualitative research, as a recruitment

tool for MIRreM newsletter subscriptions, and as a foundation for subsequent surveys. To ensure a high response rate, the completion time was limited to 3–5 minutes.

The second survey focused on identifying the types of organizations involved and their specific areas of interest, facilitating a more detailed mapping of relevant stakeholders. Following this, a third survey should be conducted to examine patterns of cooperation, employing a network survey methodology to analyse relationships and interactions among stakeholders.

This phased approach was initially designed to streamline data collection and minimize the burden on respondents. However, during implementation, it became evident that respondent pools did not necessarily overlap across survey waves. Additionally, concerns related to data protection necessitated the independence of the third survey, ensuring compliance with privacy regulations while maintaining the integrity of the research framework.

To address this problem, it was discussed to add the location of the respondents based on the IP addresses. This idea was rejected due to ethical concerns (data privacy, lack of consent from survey respondents) and also due to sources of error (the IP address does not necessarily have to match the location of the institution/person). Therefore, the information on the destination countries could not be supplemented and no statements can be made on vertical and horizontal relations of stakeholders in the field of irregular migration of specific countries. In view of the country-specific differences in governance structures, results on vertical and horizontal relations must therefore be viewed critically.

It was not possible to achieve a balanced representation of the different stakeholder types at different governance levels, which means that certain groups are overrepresented (academics/researchers), while others, such as governmental actors at provincial level, are underrepresented. The challenge of obtaining a sufficient number of responses can be attributed not only to general "survey fatigue" but also to the inherent characteristics of network surveys. Such surveys tend to be relatively abstract in nature, offering limited opportunities for participants to articulate their positions or express individual perspectives. As a result, the perceived benefits for respondents are minimal, which likely contributed to lower engagement levels. This factor may also partially explain the overrepresentation of researchers among respondents, as they are more accustomed to engaging with abstract methodological approaches and may perceive greater intrinsic value in contributing to such a study. Particularly regarding vertical and horizontal relations, there are therefore data gaps, and the significance of the results is severely limited.

Nevertheless, the added value of social network analysis as an instrument for examining network patterns among stakeholders in the field of irregular migration remains evident in multiple ways. Further elaboration on this can be found in the conclusion. Acknowledging these limitations, and as outlined in the introduction, Chapter 4 integrates relevant literature and research findings from the MIRreM project to complement the results of this study. This approach also serves to support the discussion on potential future research directions presented in the conclusion.

3. FINDINGS

Chapter 3 provides a descriptive presentation of the MIrreM network survey results, starting with the survey respondents' self-reported attributes, followed by a comparison of the characteristics of egos and alteri. From subsection 3.3 onwards, the cooperation networks in the field of irregular migration and the features of the connecting relations are discussed in more detail.

3.1 THE SURVEY RESPONDENTS

In total, 77 stakeholders in the field of irregular migration completed the survey questionnaire (See Figure 3, below). The largest proportion of the respondents are stated to work in the academic / research sector, or a think tank (44%), followed by NGOs, grassroots, faith-based organisations, or media (32%)³, and the smallest share of the respondents work in the public administration or government (23%, almost half of academic respondents).

Figure 2: Respondents' Stakeholder Types: The Area in Which They Work (n = 77)

³ In the further elaborations, these two categories, which were indicated separately in the questionnaire, were combined into one category, which consists of 24 survey respondents who indicated NGO, grassroots or faith-based organizations; and one person who indicated media.

The distribution across governance levels shows that almost half of the respondents work at the national level (48%), followed by a smaller but notable presence of the local-level (25%) and supranational-level respondents (19%), with provincial-level governance being the least represented (8%).

Figure 3: Respondents' Primary Governance Levels: The Level of Governance in Which They Operate in Their Work (n = 77)

3.1.1 Working areas

With multiple selection possible, knowledge production and knowledge transfer⁴ (knowledge production) was selected by 51 survey respondents (66%), followed by 47 respondents (61%), who have chosen policy development, policy implementation and/or advocacy⁵ (policy development). Twenty respondents (26%) indicated that service provision is their only or one of their areas of work when it comes to irregular migration.

Four stakeholders in the field of irregular migration did not select any of these three options. They stated that monitoring and advice, migration data, information provision to refugees and migrants at all stages of movement, or research on EU policies related to migration is the sole areas of work. Overall, eight respondents (10%) selected the option other⁶.

⁴ To improve readability, abbreviated as "knowledge production" in graphics and text.

⁵ To improve readability, abbreviated as "policy development" in graphics and text.

⁶ Selected area(s) of work, summarised under the category "Other" in the figure: 1) Migration data (sole area of work); 2) Monitoring and advice (sole area of work); 3) Information provision to refugees and migrants at all stages of movement (sole area of work); 4) Research on EU policies related to migration (sole area of work); 5) Piloting of innovative Governance tools (in combination with Policy

Figure 4: Respondents' All Areas of Work (Multiple Selection Answers) (n = 77)

Asked about their **primary field of work**, almost half of the respondents (46%) indicated to work primarily in the field of knowledge production, and further 36% stated to be mainly active in policy development, policy implementation and/or advocacy⁷ (policy development). Finally, for the remaining 18% of the respondents, service provision is the primary area of work.

development and Knowledge production); 6) Research, advocacy & lobbying (in combination with Policy development); 7) Counselling (in combination with Policy development and Knowledge production); 8) Legal representation (in combination with Service provision and Knowledge production)

⁷ To improve readability, abbreviated as “policy development” in graphics and text.

Figure 5: Respondents' Primary Areas of Work: Area of Involvement When It Comes to Irregular Migration (n = 72)

Among the primarily **public administration and government stakeholders**, policy development and knowledge production (33% both) are the leading areas of work. Knowledge production is the primary area of work for stakeholders in the **academic/research sector** (62%), followed by policy development (32%). NGO & media actors are the most balanced in their primary work areas, with equal shares involved in policy development and service provision (36% each) and a smaller, but notable, share in knowledge production (24%).

Figure 6: Respondents' Primary Areas of Work by Stakeholder Type

When looking at governance levels, respondents operating at the local level demonstrate a relatively balanced distribution of primary areas of work they focus on, with knowledge production being the most common (47%), followed by policy development (32%), and service provision (21%). Half of the provincial level respondents work mainly focus on policy development. Survey respondents working at the national level, same as those at the local level, predominantly work in knowledge production (43%) and policy development (35%). Respondents at the supranational level, meanwhile, overwhelmingly work in knowledge production (47%). Overall, across all governance levels, policy development and knowledge production stand out as the most prevalent areas of work among the survey respondents, while service provision is the less common area of work, particularly popular among provincial-level respondents (33%).

Figure 7: Respondents' primary area of work according to level of governance.

3.1.2 Policy area(s)

With multiple selection possible, the most prevalent policy areas of interest among the respondents of the survey include: Labour migration with 35 of the respondents (45%) indicating this policy area as one of their top three areas of interest, followed by Border control (31 respondents, or 40%) and Asylum (30 respondents, or 39%, selecting these policy areas as one of their top three areas of interest. Regularisation and social services were selected by 26 and 25 respondents, respectively (or 34% and 32%, respectively). The

least popular policy areas in the survey sample are visa policies and detention with ten respondents (13%).

The responses of the 13 respondents who selected other’ policy areas⁸ (17%) as one of the three most important areas of interest illustrate the broad spectrum of areas of work in the field of irregular migration, as well as the potential for overlaps between different policy areas.

Figure 8: Respondents’ All Policy Areas of Interest (Multiple Selection Answers) (n = 77)

⁸ The answers of the 13 respondents that chose “Other” policy areas (6.7%) as their only or one of their top three areas of interest include: Access to education; Anti-trafficking policies; Shelter, orientation, and case resolution for undocumented migrants; Relocation; Reintegration; Provision of information to refugees and migrants; Migration measurement and estimation; Integration; Health; Discrimination, racism, domestic workers, human trafficking, forced labour; Migration control, legal actions for detentions, denials of admission, or deportation orders.

When asked to identify the single **primary policy area of interest**, responses demonstrate that labour migration is the most common focus among survey respondents (25%), followed by border control (20%) and asylum (18%). Social services (12%) and return policies (11%) also have moderate representation. Regularisation (8%), visa policies (5%), and detention (1%) were less frequently selected, as the primary policy areas of interest.

Figure 9: Respondents' Primary Policy Areas of Interest Related to Irregular Migration (n = 76)

Survey respondents engaged in the public administration/government are primarily focused on border control/management and migrant smuggling policies (33%), followed by policy areas related to asylum and other protection-related policies and labour migration (17% each). In our sample, none of the public administration stakeholders have chosen access to social services for irregular migrants or detention policies as their primary policy areas of interest. Amongst the academia/research stakeholders the most prevalent policy areas of interest comprehend labour migration (29%), and border control/management and migrant smuggling (20%). Moreover, like the respondents involved in public administration/government, there are no primary interest in detention policies amongst the academia/research stakeholders as well.

Amongst NGO and Media stakeholders, the leading policy areas include labour migration, in which almost a quarter (24%) of NGO/media stakeholders are primarily involved, as well as asylum and social services (20% each). Contrary to the other stakeholder types, border control policies are not a very popular area of primary interest amongst NGO/media actors, as compared to public administration/government and academia/research stakeholders. But access to social services for irregular migrants is considerably more common compared to the share of respondents' interest in this field amongst public administration/government and academia/research stakeholders. Overall, labour migration policies are the most popular area of interest across the board, ranking high for each stakeholder type.

Figure 10: Respondents’ Primary Policy Areas of Interest Related to Irregular Migration by Stakeholder Type

Differentiated by governance level, survey respondents operating at the local level are primarily interested in asylum (32%) and labour migration (26%) policies, while respondents at the provincial governance level stated to be mainly interested in labour migration and access to social services (33% each). At the national level (the most prevalent governance level among the respondents), labour migration and border control policies are the most prevalent (24% each). Only one respondent (operating primarily at the national level) in the entire dataset indicated detention policies as the main area of interest. Among the primarily supranational level survey respondents, the main policy areas of interest include border control (33%) and labour migration (20%).

Figure 11 Respondents' Primary Policy Areas of Interest Related to Irregular Migration by Governance Level

Overall, labour migration policies are of interest across the board, while the prevalences for other policy areas of interest are distributed to specific governance levels. Regularization policies are predominantly of interest to provincial level respondents. At the national and supranational governance levels, border control policies are of primary interest to respondents, while return policies are mostly named by respondents mainly located at the national level. In the following sections, the descriptive explanations are supplemented by the network analysis including descriptions of the characteristics of the primary partners of the survey respondents and the relations between survey respondents and the primary partners they have named.

3.2 STAKEHOLDER NETWORK FINDINGS

In the following section, the network visualizations are descriptively explained. A more in-depth analysis, contextualisation and complementary presentation with results from expert interviews, stakeholder workshops and roundtables carried out as part of the MIrreM project are provided in Chapter 4.

The following graphs illustrate the key networks of stakeholders who participated in the survey. Each bubble, identified by respondents' unique ID, represents a stakeholder, with colours indicating the type (public administration, academia and research, or NGOs and media), and stakeholders are grouped within clusters accordingly. The arrows indicate the cooperation direction and intensity, showing the respondent's single most relevant connection (i.e. primary connection) either within their own cluster/bubble (intrasectoral) or across different stakeholder groups (intersectoral: different bubbles are connected by ties) and governance levels. The arrows representing relations within or between different stakeholder types can stand for one-sided or two-sided cooperation. Depending on whether the arrowhead points towards or away from the survey respondent (within the cluster or towards another cluster), the cooperation is primarily initiated by the cooperation partner or the survey respondent. Arrows with two arrowheads stand for mutual cooperations. The intensity of the cooperation (in relation to the frequency of contact, exchange) is indicated by the thickness of the arrow: The thicker the arrow, the more intensive the exchange between the cooperation partners.

3.2.1 Policy Development Network

In the network graph below, the **policy development network** is visualized and illustrates the cooperations between stakeholder types in the field of policy development, based on how respondents reported on their cooperation partners. Forty-seven respondents are involved in policy development, policy implementation and advocacy, 20 of them work in academia/research, another 20 works for NGOs or the media, and seven of them stated public administration/government as their occupation sector. Overall, most respondents within this network work in NGO/media (42.5%), or in the academia/ research field (42.5%).

Figure 12: Cooperation between primary stakeholder types within the policy development network.

Out of the forty-seven survey respondents cooperating on policy development, 25 (53%) cooperate primarily with partners within their own sector (intrasectoral), i.e. stakeholders of the same type. 22 respondents (47%) cooperate primarily with cooperation partners from other sectors (intersectoral). Survey respondents involved in **public administration** with the policy development network, predominantly cooperate with partners that are also in public administration domain: five out of seven exchange regularly either on mutual basis (three) or on the receiving end (two) of communication with other public administration actors. Another two public administration stakeholders cooperate on regular and mutual basis with their primary partners in academia/research. However, none of those seven respondents act as initiators of cooperative actions, there is no “primarily from me to partners” cooperation direction. None of the survey respondents from the public administration mapped in this policy development network stated that they cooperate with actors from NGOs/media. The information provided by the survey respondents indicate a rather homogeneous network with a focus on cooperation within the institutional framework of public administration. However, if this picture is supplemented by the information on cooperation partners provided by the survey respondents from the other working areas - almost half of the

respondents from two other working areas (academia/research, and NGOs and media) reported maintaining cooperation with public administration partners - the question arises as to whether this result is due to the limited number of survey respondents in public administration or whether the differing assessments of the respondents from the other working areas are due, for example, to a different understanding of cooperation per se.

Looking at the heterogeneity of the policy development networks of survey respondents in academia / research, it is noticeable that only one link between **academia/research stakeholders** (20 respondents) with actors from NGO/media exists. Half of the respondents (ten) involved in academia/research mainly cooperate with partners in public administration. Eight of these cooperations are stated to be equal and mutual in both directions. In total, among academia/research stakeholders working in the field of policy development, policy implementation and advocacy, most communication direction is either mutual or is initiated by the survey respondents.

The survey respondents of the stakeholder type **NGO/media** within the policy development network (20 respondents), most often cooperate either with their fellow colleagues in the NGO/media domain (eleven of twenty respondents), or with actors working in public administration (nine of twenty). Most of the interactions between NGO/media and public administration stakeholders is mutual or initiated by NGO/media stakeholders. Compared to the networks of the other stakeholder types (academia/research and public administration/government), it is apparent that respondents in the field of NGOs/media mainly report stable and intense cooperations (more than once a month / a week) with actors in public administration, comprehending three intensive cooperations (more than once a week, two both sided, one primarily initiated by the survey respondent), four medium intensive (more than once a month) reciprocal cooperations and two one-sided relation (one primarily from the cooperation partner and one primarily from the survey respondent).

All stakeholder types within the policy development network illustrate a high level of connectivity with the same stakeholder types (intrasectoral). Furthermore, in terms of intersectoral cooperation, cooperation and networking of academia/research and of NGO/media stakeholders with public administration / the governmental sector in the field of policy development, policy implementation and advocacy are significant.

Cooperation between primary governance levels

In the following network visualisation, the colours of the respondents are maintained from the previous chart and represent the respondents' stakeholder types. This network figure illustrates the distribution of different stakeholder types on different governance levels and their interactions with actors on other levels of governance, which provides insights into the share of horizontal and vertical relations within the policy development network.

Figure 13: Cooperation between primary stakeholder types across different governance levels in the field of policy development.

The stakeholder composition at the **local level** is quite diverse, consisting of actors from NGOs/media, academia/research, and public administration/government, in relatively equal proportions. The graph illustrates how survey respondents, whose primary governance level is 'local,' predominantly collaborate with actors on the same governance level (ten out of 13), mostly on a mutual and frequent basis. Three other respondents regularly cooperate on a weekly basis with supranational-level partners.

It is surprising that none of the different stakeholder types on the local level reported cooperation with actors at the provincial or the national level. Conversely, different stakeholder types from all governance levels reported cooperations with actors at the local level: exchange with NGO/media actors from the national governance level (three) is more common (two mainly initiated / maintained by the survey respondents on national level.)

At the **provincial level**, the smallest cohort (four respondents who indicated provincial as their primary level of governance in this policy development network) includes mostly NGO/media representatives and one actor from academia/research and is therefore quite homogenous. Half of the provincial-level respondents primarily collaborate with local-level partners on a mutual, monthly basis. The other half engages with fellow provincial-level

partners: one partnership is mutual and occurs monthly, while the other is annual, with cooperation directed toward the respondent.

Within the policy development network, most respondents operate at the **national level** (24 out of 47, or roughly 51%). Among them, 79% (19 out of 24) primarily collaborate with fellow national-level partners. The remaining three national-level respondents cooperate with local-level partners, either taking the lead in cooperative efforts or engaging in mutual exchanges. Two other national-level respondents work primarily with supranational partners: one partnership is mutual on a quarterly basis, while the other is monthly, with the national-level respondents acting as the primary initiators of cooperation and information exchange.

At the **supranational level**, five out of six respondents primarily work in academia or research, another one in public administration. Half of these respondents exchange regularly (weekly or monthly) on a mutual basis with partners who also operate at the supranational level. Two others primarily connect with national-level partners, one cooperation is reciprocal and of medium intensity (more than once a quarter/year), the other cooperation is one-sided (primarily initiated by the partner on national level) and of medium intensity (more than once per month). One survey respondent at the supranational level reported to cooperate reciprocally on a medium intensive basis (more than once a month) with a local-level partner.

Overall, the policy development network shows that respondents tend to collaborate most frequently with partners operating at the same governance level and cooperations are mainly very intensive (more than once a week) and of medium intensity (more than once a month). Nonetheless, actors of all governance levels stated cooperations with other governance levels. Yet, the extent of cooperation between the various governance levels is lower than expected, particularly regarding the inclusion of the provincial level in cooperation efforts.

3.2.2 Service Provision Network

The **Service Provision Network** consists of 20 survey respondents, who identified 'service provision' as their area of work, with the majority (65%) working in NGOs and the media sector.

Figure 14: Cooperations between primary stakeholder types in the field of service provision.

Most respondents working in **NGOs and media** (ten out of 13) primarily collaborate with their peers in the same sector (intrasectoral). These partnerships are characterized by equal and mutual exchanges of different intensity. The remaining three respondents in this area mainly cooperate with partners in the public administration.

Among the four respondents in **public administration**, two regularly collaborate with partners in NGOs and media, while the other two primarily cooperate with colleagues also involved in public administration.

All three **academia/research** stakeholders in this network engage in two-way collaborations with both NGO/media and public administration.

The stakeholder network in the area of service provision is characterized by a strong representation of persons in the NGOs and media sector, which is reasonable considering that NGOs are generally strongly represented as service providers in the field of irregular migration. Based on this, it is also reasonable that a large part of the cooperative relationships take place within this working area, and that many partnerships are located within this field. Considering that the governmental sector also plays a crucial role as a service provider in the area of irregular migration (e.g., managing registration processes, access to health services and education etc.), the limitations of the data material become apparent here, as only four of the survey respondents from this field of work are represented.

Cooperation between primary governance levels

Within the service provision network, as in the policy development network, most respondents primarily operate at either the national or local levels of governance.

Figure 15: Cooperations between primary stakeholder types across governance levels in the field of service provision.

In total, three stakeholders from the public administration, three actors from the working area NGOs and media and one survey respondent from the academic/research area have located their work primarily at the **local level**: a quite heterogenous composition of stakeholders. Among these respondents, all stated primarily collaborating with stakeholders in the field of irregularity at the same governance level. These collaborations occur regularly, with participants either initiating information exchanges or engaging in equal cooperative efforts with their partners.

The three **provincial-level** respondents (two in the field of NGOs and media, one academic/research) engage in equal partnerships with colleagues across three different governance levels: local, provincial, and supranational.

Most **national-level** respondents in the service provision network are involved in NGOs or media (nine out of ten, one actor's main working area is academic/research), with six of them collaborating primarily with fellow national-level colleagues. The sole academia stakeholder operating at the national level in this network reports infrequent two-way communication (once a year) with a primary partner at the local level. Two other national-level respondents, both working in NGOs/media, maintain regular, mutual cooperation with their supranational partners.

The only respondent (academia/research) operating at the **supranational level** reports weekly, mutual collaboration with a partner at the local level.

Overall, within the service provision network, all different governance levels are interconnected, except for the national and provincial level. Actors at national and supranational level occupy a central position in terms of the number of governance-level overarching ties in this network; on the local and again on the national governance level, the relevance of cooperations among service providers within the same governance level is illustrated.

3.2.3 Knowledge Production Network

The knowledge production network is the largest, with 51 respondents engaged in this work area within the field of irregular migration. Unsurprisingly, the majority of these respondents work in academia and research (nearly 57%), followed by 27% in NGOs/media, and the remaining 15% in public administration/the government sector.

Figure 16: Cooperations between primary stakeholder types in the field of knowledge production.

Respondents involved in **academia and research** mostly collaborate (18 survey respondents) with colleagues in the same field. But beyond these cooperations with the same stakeholder type, five respondents stated to have cooperation partners in the public administration, four of them maintain an equal and mutual cooperation with their partners of very intensive and medium intensive frequency. Another five academic/ research stakeholders reported cooperations with NGOs and media, three of the cooperations being two-sided with a very intensive and medium intensive frequency.

The network graph illustrates that also stakeholders in the field of **NGOs and media** maintain various intersectoral cooperations in the field of knowledge production (seven), mainly with academic/research stakeholders (five of in total seven cooperations outside the working area NGOs and media; two of the cooperations are with actors of public administration, which are reciprocal and of very high and medium intensity). Seven stakeholders reported intrasectoral cooperations of different intensity, in the majority of cases two-sided.

Those respondents working in **public administration** primarily engage in intrasectoral cooperation (six out of eight), meaning their primary partners also operate within the public administration sector. Two cooperations with the academic/research sector are one-sided,

from the respondent in the public administration to the cooperation partner in the academic/research sector; one relation with the NGOs and media working area is reciprocal, but of low frequency (more than once in a quarter/year).

Overall, the knowledge productions network is characterized by a high number of intrasectoral ties, particularly between stakeholders within the academia and research sector, as well as by ties between academia/research stakeholders and public administration and between academia/research stakeholders and NGOs/media, while public administration/government and NGOs/media are only connected by three reciprocal relations of different intensity.

Cooperation between primary governance levels

Fifty-one survey respondents stated to work in the field of **knowledge production**, including eight stakeholders from public administration, 14 actors from NGOs/media and the majority, 29 persons, are in the academic/research sector. Within the knowledge production network, most respondents primarily operate at either the national or local levels of government: approximately half of them focus on the national level (51%), while about a quarter work mainly at the local level (24%). At the supranational level (9 actors, eight of them from academia/research), respondents tend to collaborate with either their colleagues at the supranational level (four cooperations) or with partners at the national level (five cooperations). Three of the relations with actors on the national level, two of them reciprocal, are of low frequency (once a year or less, more than once in a quarter/year).

Figure 17: Cooperations between primary stakeholder types across governance levels in the field of knowledge production.

Those operating primarily at the **national level** (12 actors from academia/research, eight actors from the NGOs/media and six actors from the public administration) maintain cooperative relationships across all four levels of government, but the majority of the respondents (16 out of 26) cooperate with partners on the same governance level. It is also noticeable that five out of six of the stakeholders from the public administration maintain cooperation primarily within their own governance level. Among the nine cooperations outside the own governance level of actors, four are maintained with partners on the supranational level. One cooperation partner is located on the provincial level (reciprocal, low intensity) and another six cooperations with the local level are mainly two-sided (five out of six) and of higher intensity (more than once a week, more than once a month).

The **provincial level** has the lowest number of actors, as well as only a small number of relations with other governance levels. The two collaborations stated by the actors on provincial level with the local governance level are of low and very low frequency.

Thirteen survey respondents located themselves on the **local level**: seven from academia/research, four from the NGO/media sector and another two from public administration. The majority (eight) stated to cooperate within the local level, six out of the eight stated to have two-sided cooperations of high or very high frequency. The cooperations of the four actors from NGOs/media only focus on the local level, without any relations with other governance levels. Of the four relationships emanating from this level, three connect with the supranational level.

Overall, the knowledge production network demonstrates extensive cooperation across governance levels. What is striking here is the relevance of the national level, which on the one hand has the largest number of cooperations outside its own governance level - it should be noted that the national level is the most strongly represented - but the national level also has the largest number of ties originating from actors at other governance levels. Another striking feature is that the provincial level is not only poorly represented among the survey respondents, but also that only one relation (located on the national level) was stated by the survey respondents at other governance levels with the provincial level.

Overall, across all three networks, all stakeholder types tend to cooperate primarily within their own sectors and governance levels. The low significance of actors at provincial level as network partners for actors at other governance levels is also consistently apparent.

An in-depth analysis of network cooperation, particularly regarding intrasectoral cooperation and networks across different governance levels, is the subject of the following sections.

3.3 ANALYSIS OF COOPERATION: PRIMARY STAKEHOLDER TYPES

The following section provides a more detailed description of the key characteristics of the networks, differentiated by stakeholder type (public administration, academia/research, and NGOs/media). The focus here is on vertical (across different governance levels) and horizontal (within one governance level) cooperations; intersectoral (between different stakeholder types) and intrasectoral (within one stakeholder type) relations; the intensity of cooperations; as well as the direction of the cooperation.

3.3.1 Governance Level Interactions: Vertical And Horizontal Relationships

Figure 23 illustrates vertical and horizontal stakeholder cooperations. While horizontal cooperations are within one governance level, vertical cooperations comprehend upward connections (in the figure shortly 'Up') - if respondent's level of governance is lower than that of his/her partner (for example, if respondent operates at local level, and his/her partner operates at national level), as well as downward cooperations (in the figure shortly 'Down'), i.e. cooperations with partners at a lower governance level.

Figure 18: Horizontal and vertical cooperations: primary stakeholder types.

The network of stakeholders in the academia/research sector has a relatively good balance of both horizontal (58%) and vertical (42%) primary relationships between the partners, with ‘down’ connections being twice as prevalent as the ‘up’ connections. The NGO/media and public administration networks, on the other hand, prefer horizontal partnerships. Among the vertical connections, NGO/Media respondents lean towards ‘downward’ connections, whilst the respondents from public administration prioritize more ‘upward’ connections. Within the NGO/media network, horizontal networks predominate, with 72% of connections/partnerships taking place between partners operating at the same governance levels. The network of stakeholders in public administration has the lowest proportion of vertical connections (26%), and the highest proportion of horizontal connections (74%), meaning that within this network most partnerships took place among the stakeholders operating at the same levels of governance.

3.3.2 Stakeholder Type Interactions: Intersectoral And Intrasectoral Networks

Intrasectoral networks describe cooperations that take place between respondents and partners of the same stakeholder type (e.g., both are in Academia) and are coded by ‘0’. Intersectoral networks include different types of stakeholders, then the variable is equal to ‘1’.

Figure 19: Intrasectoral and intersectoral cooperations: primary stakeholder types.

Stakeholders in **public administration** have the highest proportion of intrasectoral connections (63%). Hence, public administration cooperations mainly take place within the own sector. The **NGO/media network** is relatively balanced, but also tends to lean towards the intrasectoral connections (57% each). Also, cooperations of actors in the **academic/research** field have a nearly balanced distribution, but slightly lean towards intrasectoral connections (52%). Overall, the intrasectoral cooperations tend to predominate over the partnerships between different types of stakeholders, this is particularly evident in the public administration network.

3.3.3 Cooperation Intensity / Frequency Of Contact

The intensity of cooperation was measured based on the frequency of contact between the primary cooperation partners. It was differentiated between contacts on a weekly, monthly, quarterly and yearly basis.

Figure 20: Contact frequency: primary stakeholder types.

In terms of frequency of cooperation/communication between survey respondents and cooperation partners, weekly and monthly contact are the most common communication patterns across all stakeholder types.

Stakeholders in the **field of public administration** have the highest proportion of weekly communication (53%), meaning that more than half of the cooperation between partners within this network occurs on weekly basis. Monthly communication is also quite prevalent within this network (31.5%). **Academia/research** stakeholders generally prioritize monthly communication (38%), although communications on weekly basis are also common (a quarter, or 25%). Moreover, this network exhibits a more varied distribution across all frequencies: 21% of communication, for example, occurs on quarterly basis, and 12% happens on annual basis, whereas such communication frequencies are very uncommon among public administration and NGO/media stakeholders. Finally, among the **NGO/Media network**, communication intensity predominantly happens on monthly basis (45%), or weekly basis (34%), i.e., on more regular basis.

3.3.4 Cooperation Direction

The direction of communication provides information on whether the primary cooperation is predominantly initiated and maintained from one side, i.e. originating from the survey respondent or the cooperation partner; or whether the cooperation is driven forward by both sides to the same extent (equal and mutual).

Figure 21: Cooperation direction: primary stakeholder types.

Across all three networks, mutual partnerships dominate, with approximately 60% of communication occurring on a two-way, reciprocal basis, with the highest share of mutual communication occurring within the academia/research network. Furthermore, the patterns of communication are alike across all stakeholders’ specific networks: cooperations initiated by the survey respondents are followed in frequency after mutual cooperations, while cooperation initiated by the cooperation partners are the least commonly reported. A more detailed comparison between the different stakeholder networks shows that in the NGO/media sector, the respondents stated to be commonly the initiators of cooperative efforts and information exchange compared to the other stakeholder networks. In the public administration network, by comparison, the survey respondents are most commonly the recipients of collaborative efforts and information exchange.

3.4 ANALYSIS OF COOPERATION: AREAS OF WORK

In a further step, we subsequently analyse the characteristics of the primary networks differentiated by working areas (Policy Development, Service Provision, and Knowledge Production). This allows us to supplement the analysis according to stakeholder types and provides insights into the cooperation between and within relevant fields of work in the area of irregular migration.

3.4.1 Governance Level Interactions: Vertical And Horizontal Relationships

The following graph illustrates the distribution of horizontal and vertical relations differentiated according to the three main working areas. Across all work areas specific networks’ horizontal cooperations dominate in the cases of the policy development network and the service provision network, horizontal cooperations make up about 70%. In the network knowledge production, horizontal connections still make up the largest share (59%) but compared to the other two other work area-specific networks, vertical connections have a share of 41%, compared to around 30% in the service provision and the policy development network. Overall, for all three types of networks, horizontal connections tend to dominate over vertical connections.

Figure 22: Horizontal and vertical cooperations: work areas.

3.4.2 Stakeholder Type Interactions: Intersectoral And Intrasectoral Networks

As with the previous differentiation by stakeholder type, in contrast to the other network characteristics, a differentiation of the networks by work area shows a relatively balanced distribution of intrasectoral and intersectoral collaborations across all work areas. The greatest share of intrasectoral connections (between the same stakeholder type) are present in the service provision network (60%), closely followed by the knowledge production network (57%), while the policy development network has the highest amount of intersectoral connections, of 47% (in the knowledge production network 43%). However, overall, across all three of these networks, the respondents lean towards same stakeholder type cooperations.

Figure 23: Intrasectoral and intersectoral cooperations: work areas.

3.4.3 Cooperation Intensity / Frequency of Contact

In terms of the frequency of contact in the work areas specific networks, it is noticeable that weekly cooperation is only dominant in the service provision network, although it should be noted that this category is the least represented by survey respondents and in figures this makes a difference of two people compared to monthly communication. Overall, the service provision and policy development network have a share of about 80% of weekly and monthly contact frequency, while the network knowledge production network has a share of 60%, and a higher share of quarterly contacts (24%, compared to 15% in the other two networks). The policy development network shows a predominance of monthly interactions (49%), with a significant portion of communication within the network also occurring weekly (34%).

In the work area service provision, the highest weekly contact frequency (45%) is visible, suggesting a strong and consistent level of interaction. Knowledge production has the lowest weekly engagement (27%) compared to the other networks, highlighting a more intermittent communication pattern. This finding can be placed in the context of the different work cycles of services and research/academia: While the provision of services requires a higher intensity of contact, longer throughput times are required in research/academia for the production of

knowledge. Yearly interactions are relatively low across all networks, with knowledge production having the highest at 10%, while policy development has the lowest at 2%.

Figure 24: Cooperation frequency: work areas.

3.4.4 Cooperation Direction

All three networks show a high share of reciprocal cooperations, between 60 and 61%, with the highest percentage in in the service provision based cooperations (65%). The percentage of contacts ‘from me to partners’ is relatively consistent across the networks, with policy development at 32%, service provision at 30%, and knowledge production at 29%. Contacts ‘from partners to me’ are notably low in all networks, with service provision at just 5%, policy development at 9%, and knowledge production at 10%.

Figure 25: Cooperation direction: work areas.

3.5 ANALYSIS OF COOPERATION: PRIMARY LEVELS OF GOVERNANCE (LOCAL, PROVINCIAL, NATIONAL, AND SUPRANATIONAL)

Following the analysis focuses on the primary levels of governance, comprehending primary stakeholder types and their cooperation across (vertical) and within (horizontal) the governance levels; the extent and limitations of intersectoral and intrasectoral exchange; the frequency of information exchange; and the cooperation direction.

3.5.1 Governance Level Interactions: Vertical And Horizontal Relationships

The analysis of vertical and horizontal cooperations illustrates especially on local level a strong horizontal orientation (79%). Also, the national networks mainly operate on the same governance level (69%). By comparison, in provincial and supranational networks, vertical connections dominate (on provincial level 60% and on supranational level 56%). Considering that in the cases of the local and supranational networks vertical cooperations are only possible either downwards (supranational network) or upwards (local network), it is notable that in the supranational network 56% of the relations are vertical, while on the local level the share of vertical relations only makes 21%. In addition, vertical and horizontal cooperations are most balanced at supranational level and have the largest gap at local level (total vertical 21% and total horizontal 79%).

Overall, the local and national networks emphasize horizontal collaboration, while Provincial and Supranational networks show stronger vertical structures, particularly in downward communication.

Figure 26: Vertical and horizontal cooperations: governance level.

3.5.2 Stakeholder Type Interactions: Intersectoral And Intrasectoral Networks

In terms of interactions within and across sectors, differences are also observed across the governance levels. At the local level, the different stakeholder types maintain a relatively balanced share of intrasectoral (48%) and intersectoral (52%) collaborative connections, which points to a heterogenous composition of stakeholders. By comparison, stakeholders at the national and provincial have mainly intrasectoral networks, indicating that most connections are between stakeholder of the same type. Actors on the supranational level maintain the highest proportion of intersectoral networks (62.5%), meaning that most connections within this governance level are between different stakeholder types.

Figure 27: Intersectoral and intrasectoral cooperations: governance level.

3.5.3 Cooperation Intensity / Frequency Of Contact

In terms of the cooperation intensity, locally based networks favour frequent communication, with more than half of the communication between partners taking place on weekly basis (78%). Compared to networks in other governance levels, the most frequent/intensive collaboration takes place at the local level, with more than 90% of interactions occurring on a weekly or monthly basis. In the networks on provincial (50%), national (39%) and supranational level (44%), monthly communication patterns dominate. National networks exhibit a diverse engagement pattern, but mainly engage monthly (39%), quarterly (29%), and weekly (24%) in cooperation interactions. Supranational networks also focus on regular interactions with their communication happening either monthly (44%) or weekly (31%), however quarterly communications are common as well (19%). Overall, all network (governance level) prioritize more frequent interactions with their respective partners.

Figure 28: Contact frequency: governance level.

3.5.4 Cooperation Direction

Across all levels, mutual cooperation is the most prevalent, particularly among provincial (80%) and supranational (75%) levels. This is suggestive of collaborative, reciprocal interactions across all levels of governance in the field of irregular migration. Both local and national have higher proportions of “primarily from me to partners” than “primarily from my partners to me” direction of cooperation, suggesting a proactive stance in initiating cooperation. This could indicate a leadership role in cooperations and/or a larger sphere of influence on other levels. In contrast, cooperations located on supranational and provincial level show equally balanced “primarily from me to partners” and “primarily from my partners to me” proportions, indicative of more balanced exchange of cooperative efforts.

Figure 29: Cooperation direction: governance level.

4. SUPPLEMENTING FINDINGS WITH LITERATURE AND RESEARCH

Based on the descriptive explanations and the visual (network) illustrations in the previous chapters, conclusions can be drawn about the composition of the networks⁹, especially regarding the heterogeneity (in terms of different attributes/characteristics) or homogeneity of the actors in a network, and their modes of cooperation (intensity, direction). About the cooperation that were named by the survey respondents, the data collection was limited to a small number of characteristics, namely the stakeholder type and the governance level. All stakeholder types and all governance levels are represented in all three networks by main activity field, albeit to varying degrees. Due to the limitations of the available data and therefore reduced validity, this chapter supplements the findings with literature and further research results. A particular focus was placed on identifying possible starting points for further (network research) and related questions, which are set out in the conclusion section.

Stakeholder cooperations in the field of policy development

Regarding the heterogeneity of stakeholders' relations of the policy development network in the field of irregular migration, a relatively balanced distribution of intrasectoral and intersectoral collaborations can be seen. However, a closer and overall look at the network visualisation reveals some striking features regarding the diversity of the stakeholders and their partners, as well as the relations. On the one hand, all stakeholder types have a high proportion of cooperations with the same stakeholder type and thus intrasectoral relations. The intersectoral cooperations emphasise the importance of cooperations with the public administration and the governmental sector in the field of policy development, policy implementation and advocacy: stakeholders from the NGO/media work area only reported cooperations with stakeholders from the public administration (nine ties). Except for one connection with the NGO/media sector, the academia/research stakeholders also consistently referred to cooperation with actors from public administration (ten ties). Survey respondents from public administration, in contrast, only reported (reciprocal) contacts with actors from academia/research (two relationships, although the small number of cases - seven survey respondents - must be noted here). However, when looking at the overall picture, all stakeholder types are connected, but the connection between academia/research actors and NGOs/media actors is based on only one (one-sided) relationship.

⁹ The composition gives information about characteristic attributes, for example, the proportion of governmental and academic professionals in a network (Marin and Wellman 2011:21).

This result emphasises the importance of intrasectoral cooperations within public administration and the governmental sector in the areas of policy making and policy implementation in the field of irregular migration and also illustrates the involvement of the different stakeholder types in these processes. In addition, the high number of reciprocal and intensive relationships between academia/research stakeholders with the public administration/government as well as between NGOs/media and the public administration/government points to equal, mutual and collaborative cooperations in this field.

The cooperation between academia and public administration points to the mutual exchange of expert knowledge, research findings as well as of data, which might have different purposes differing by stakeholder types. Research findings and expert knowledge from the academic/research sector might contribute to policy development and strategies of policy implementation (“evidence-based policymaking”) (Scholten, 2018). But furthermore, , i.e. research on (irregular) migration is impacted by e.g. funding structures, which might influence how migration research is done, which “questions” are asked, which theories are implemented and related to policymakers (Scholten, 2018). Governmental institutions often award research contracts across various policy areas, with the findings subsequently informing policy development and implementation. Funding-related reporting obligations contribute to the establishment and continuity of relationships between policymakers and researchers. The relationship between social science research and politics is complex, characterized by normative debates and empirical observations. Policymakers often critique research for its lack of direct utility, while researchers emphasize their role in enlightening policy decisions, though their work is frequently overlooked or selectively utilized (Scholten, 2018). The precise influence of evidence on policy decisions remains unclear, as does whether research drives policy, aligns with pre-existing plans, or is engaged with by policymakers in symbolic or direct ways. This ongoing challenge of measuring the impact of science on policymaking can be complemented by examining the science-policy relationship as a central dimension (Edler et al., 2022).

Including NGOs and civil society organizations in this framework broadens the analysis, revealing the influence of advocacy and other forms of civil society engagement in policy development and advocacy. Civil society organizations, alongside other competing actors, play a significant role in influencing policy, especially in the context of migration. MIRreM country experts highlight the influential role of civil society in advocating for more liberal migration policies, particularly in countries like Belgium, Canada, Germany, Ireland, Morocco, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Tunisia (Hendow et al., 2024). These groups, often working alongside private and local actors, have been central in pushing for progressive changes in migration policy. Advocacy activities seek to influence decision-makers directly or indirectly through public opinion or the dissemination of alternative policy models. While NGOs are vital in encouraging citizen participation and holding governments accountable, they also face challenges due to competing interests and their own controversial political nature (Casey, 2014). The relationship between governmental institutions and NGOs is marked by tension, stemming from differing objectives, agendas, and dependencies, including the outsourcing of tasks and related funding schemes. Additionally, NGOs may unintentionally or intentionally provide data through funding-related project reports and

cooperation, though such dynamics may create barriers to intersectoral cooperation, particularly in the realm of data usage (Slootjes & Sohst, 2024).

Considering the broad definition of cooperation and especially with regard to the exchange of data and information, the cooperations between local and national as well as supranational level can be explained, as EU and national policies are implemented at local level and data as well as information and data flow in both directions. The apparently strong focus on horizontal cooperation can also be seen in the context of policy implementation, which requires strong cooperation between the actors at a governance level as well as the same stakeholder types (public administration, governmental institutions). This also provides a coherent picture in view of the high number of reciprocal and intensive cooperations, intersectoral as well as intrasectoral between stakeholders of public administration and NGOs/media. Of the total of 27 ties in public administration and NGOs/media, 17 are two-sided and three of these are intrasectoral in the area of public administration, while in the NGO/media work area five of the reciprocal relationships are intrasectoral.

Especially in the work area policy development, policy implementation and advocacy findings the MIRREM project provide complementary explanations of network structures and the non- or limited existence of ties between some stakeholder types and governance levels.

The numerous ties between academia and public administration, as well as between NGOs/media and public administration, indicate that different stakeholders are involved in policy development, policy implementation and advocacy, considering the number of reciprocal relations with high intensity. Therefore, this exchange seems to be systemically and structurally anchored. Intersectoral cooperation can, for example, be based on the funding of (research) projects that evaluate policy measures in the field of irregular migration and thus influence policy development; it can refer to different bodies that involve multiple stakeholders, or also include the (project) reports and related exchanges of NGOs that exist on challenges related to policies.

The diverse array of stakeholders and administrative levels, along with varying interpretations of measures and legislation, can lead to coordination challenges, tensions, and competition among actors. These issues are associated with slow implementation and limited effectiveness of policy measures. In migration governance, different stakeholders have distinct objectives and approaches, and the resulting tensions significantly impact the implementation of migration policies (Hendow et al., 2024).

However, our data does not reveal which roles and activities the various stakeholders assume in this context, e.g. whether cooperation between public administration and NGOs focuses on one of the areas (policy development, policy implementation or advocacy) or to what extent information and data from the academic/research sector and from NGOs/media actually flow into policy development and implementation, i.e. what impact this exchange actually has.

MIRREM research highlights issues related to data non-usage and underusage, including concerns over data reliability, representativeness, and politicization (Slootjes & Sohst, 2024). Data may not be shared due to fears of misuse, lack of trust, or irrelevance, and gaps in data about sub-groups or local contexts persist. Concerns over politicization, influenced

by shifting political landscapes, are also evident, with right-wing governments imposing restrictions, especially during various crises (Hendow et al., 2024). Additionally, data producers, particularly service providers and NGOs, often fear loss of control over their data, leading to reluctance in sharing information with other stakeholders, including researchers and government entities. These factors contribute to barriers in cooperation and data exchange across sectors.

Furthermore, Hendow et al. (2024) report that data availability issues hinder informed policy development and evidence-based assessments of policy effectiveness. Gaps in data also obstruct implementation, particularly in return and regularisation policies.

The service provision network

In the service provision network survey respondents from the work area NGO/media are predominantly represented. The survey respondents from the NGO/media work area were clearly dominated by horizontal (ten out of thirteen) and intrasectoral cooperations (again ten out of 13). Horizontal cooperations also dominate among the NGOs/media survey respondents when differentiated according to governance level: at local level, all three NGOs/media respondents represented maintain horizontal relations, at provincial level (two) one actor and at national level six out of eight. While the horizontal cooperations predominantly involve a higher frequency of exchange, but a relatively balanced ratio of reciprocal and one-sided relations, the intrasectoral cooperations and NGOs/media are predominantly two-sided (seven out of ten) and of high or medium intensity. These findings are consistent with findings of Hendow et al., (2024) and Sloopjes et al. (2023) that NGOs cooperate with each other to a high degree. This can concern the pursuit of shared goals, the implementation of projects, the referral of clients to other NGOs for certain services or also the exchange of data, information/experience. An organization's goals and strategies are often negotiated, and these are typically the driving force behind NGOs forming collaborative arrangements like networks and coalitions (Yanacopulos, 2005). On the one hand, this can explain the high significance of intrasectoral cooperations visible in the network, but on the other, it also provides an additional perspective on intersectoral cooperations and the possible underlying motives.

The public administration also maintains horizontal cooperations in the network service provision at local level (three actors), two actors referred to intersectoral relations with stakeholders from NGO/media (two further relations are intrasectoral). Funding schemes (allocation and processing) at local or even national governance level can cause NGOs/media stakeholders to interact primarily with the public administration at the same governance level for different purposes.

Services provided by public administration also involve an exchange between governmental actors with different areas of activity within the public administration; this also includes the associated exchange of data and information, as well as cooperation with NGOs/media; in the network presentation differentiated by stakeholders, five relationships take place between stakeholders from the public administration and NGOs/media, although only one of these is a two-sided relationship; all relationships are of high or medium frequency. This can also be linked to project funding and the associated reporting obligations and cooperation, as well as to a complementary range of services offered by NGOs and the public

administration. Project cooperation and project funding thus represent a central interface between governmental and NGO actors and also involve the exchange of information, data and experience both intersectorally and beyond governance levels. At the same time barriers to exchange or a selective exchange of different stakeholder types must also be assumed.

Cooperations between NGOs and the public administration and government sector are also characterized by different dependencies. Governments depend on NGOs for essential services to migrants and refugees, especially in times of crisis, granting them credibility, resources, and influence (Spencer, 2017). Vice versa external funding is crucial for the survival and growth of NGOs. They seek support from governments, corporations, the private sector, and wealthy individuals.

Funding is not neutral and can be self-serving. NGO managers must navigate external funding, including reporting obligations and compliance with conditions, such as target group definitions (Vincent, 2006). While broad definitions of target groups of services can enable access for irregular migrants without requiring documentation, narrow definitions may exclude them, leading NGOs to withhold related data (Slootjes, Kokkermans et al., 2023). NGOs are often reluctant to share data with government bodies due to confidentiality concerns, legal grey areas, and the risk of exposing irregular migrants to deportation (Slootjes & Sohst, 2024; Slootjes, Sohst et al., 2023). MIRreM research findings reveal that service providers fear government intervention and prioritize maintaining migrant trust and service access (Hendow et al., 2024). Local governments also face challenges in providing services to irregular migrants. Cities play a critical role in managing irregular migration by offering mainstream services and funding NGOs when direct provision is restricted. Some municipalities also facilitate legal assistance to mitigate exclusion (Cherti et al., 2024).

Network data illustrates that only a small number (three actors) from the field of academia/research are represented in the service provision network, who indicated two reciprocal relationships with NGOs/media actors and one reciprocal relationship with the public administration. On the one hand, researchers are rarely involved in service provision, but on the other this reveals a limitation in the interpretation of the data set due to the definition of stakeholder types: a person can, for example, be based in a research unit in the public administration or in an NGO. Cooperation with other stakeholders can therefore also be part of the aforementioned fields of cooperation between public administration and NGOs (inter- and intrasectional) or also represent a dimension in the implementation of research.

However, if the entire connections are considered, regardless of which stakeholder type has named it, all three stakeholder types in the service provision are associated with relationships of varying intensity, although there is a focus on horizontal and intrasectional cooperations as well as on cooperations between the public administration and NGOs/media actors.

The knowledge production network

Diversity, migration and integration research finds itself in a complex network of relationships with politics and civil society due to multiple factors, such as its social and political implications as well as the corresponding environment and ongoing social discourse. Even though academics and researchers are most strongly represented in the MIRreM

network stakeholder survey, it must be considered that non-academic actors producing knowledge on migration have grown rapidly, challenging academics who face counter-knowledge from social movements and the influence of digital methods controlled by policy and private sectors. As a result, academics no longer dominate transnational migration research (Amelung et al., 2024).

The MIRreM stakeholders' knowledge production network is dominated by actors from academia/research and visualizes the relevance of cooperations between public administration and academia/research stakeholders (seven relations). The relations between research and policy must also always be set in the respective historical, institutional and current context and are therefore dynamic and changeable. Cooperation between research and policymakers can be characterized by certain tensions on the one hand but might be also an environment allowing the co-production of knowledge (Entzinger & Scholten, 2015). Although the findings from the MIRreM network survey do not allow any insights into country-specific contexts, they confirm that despite the politicization of migration and diversity and the associated challenges in knowledge production, relationships between policy makers and researchers are not disrupted, but reconfigured (Scholten, 2018). The relevance of civil society actors and cooperation with science and research is also reflected in the extent and characteristics of relations (11) between these stakeholder types in the knowledge production stakeholder network.

Another noticeable feature of this network is that public administration and NGOs/media are only connected via three relations (all two-sided and of different intensity). This clearly distinguishes the knowledge production network from the two networks already described. The low number of relations between public administration and NGOs/media can also be explained by the handling of sensitive data and the different interests, objectives and areas of responsibility (Slootjes & Sohst, 2024). It must also be taken into account that NGOs sometimes operate in a legal grey area when they include irregular migrants among their clientele and the transfer of data, experiences and information is therefore limited to reporting obligations. From the perspective of public administration, it should also be noted that NGOs/media are not subject to the same framework conditions as actors from academia/research, e.g. that precise information is provided in advance for what purpose and is used, the obligation to maintain an objective perspective, the protection of interview partners, etc. through anonymisation, pseudonymisation, etc. The work of NGOs and the media, especially public relations work, which is essential in order to raise donations, for example, usually involves clear positioning and the associated framing of messages. The framework conditions and specifications in academia/research described above therefore represent a specific framework for cooperation with actors from science and research, which can also contain added value for all stakeholder types that also draw on research results for their work.

In the area of knowledge production, too, there is a relatively balanced relationship between intersectoral and intrasectoral connections among stakeholders in academia/research and NGOs/media. Yet, in the public administration/the governmental sector, intrasectoral relationships predominate among the eight survey respondents (six out of eight). This can be interpreted to mean that, on the one hand, public administration works to a large extent with administrative data, for which the purpose and data protection must be taken into account and therefore, in many cases, disclosure is only possible within public administration. On the

other hand, aggregated data that is accessible to the public and the scientific community is often not passed on via bilateral relations but published and disseminated via channels such as public databases and governmental websites.

In addition, it should be considered that national, but predominantly EU-level, funding has led to an increase in knowledge production in recent years, as well as supporting intersectoral and intrasectoral networking. The European Union actively develops and supports migration policies through legal frameworks, funding schemes, and guidelines. EU institutions have fostered a robust ecosystem of science-policy collaboration, promoting “evidence-informed” policymaking by creating resources and infrastructures for data and statistics. Initiatives like MIPEX and OECD/EU integration indicators exemplify their role as (co)patrons of research-policy efforts. Through Framework Programmes, significant resources are allocated to migration research, reflecting growing demand for data to predict and manage cross-border mobility. These trends have influenced social sciences and humanities research, steering agendas toward policy-relevant work aligned with EU priorities (Dodevska, 2024). This is also reflected in the high level of vertical relations (total 41%; up: 16% and down: 25%) compared with the service provision and policy development networks (graph see p. 49) and the intersectoral (48%) relations, which are almost on a par with the intrasectoral relations compared with the two other work area-related networks (see graph p. 45).

5. CONCLUSIONS, CRITICAL REFLECTION AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This work was guided by the key objectives to conduct a comparative analysis and visualization of cooperation frameworks along both horizontal and vertical axes of policymaking, capturing the nature and intensity of stakeholder interactions in the field of irregular migration. It aimed to map and illustrate stakeholder ties and areas of cooperation across various governance levels, including the EU, national, provincial, and local contexts. This visual and analytical representation was enriched by a comparative examination of how these cooperation frameworks are interconnected with data usage, data production, and governance structures, drawing on complementing literature and further research findings of the MIrreM project.

The study's key findings provide initial insights into stakeholders' vertical and horizontal cooperation, within and across different sectors, in policy development, service provision, and knowledge production in the field of irregular migration. The analysis illustrates both the collaborative nature and structural tensions within and between sectors, giving an idea about the patterns of interaction and the power asymmetries that shape these relationships.

Taking into account the limitations of this work (see Chapter 2: Methodology), particular attention is paid to the potential value of this work as a starting point for future research to deepen the understanding of cooperation dynamics and their long-term implications.

Key findings

Regarding stakeholder cooperations in the field of policy development, the survey results highlight the crucial role of intrasectoral cooperation within public administration and government in policy making and implementation in the field of irregular migration. It also shows the active involvement of various stakeholders. Additionally, the numerous reciprocal and intensive relationships between academia/research and public administration/government, as well as between NGOs/media and public administration/government, indicate strong, mutual, and collaborative partnerships in this area. However, what these results do not capture, but literature and findings from focus groups and experts interviews conducted as part of the MIRREM project, is that funding-related relationships between public administration/government and academia/research, as well as between public administration/government and NGOs, can be characterized by tensions, information gaps, limited communication, and conflicting objectives (Hendow et al., 2024; Scholten, 2018; Slootjes, Sohst, et al., 2023; Slootjes & Sohst, 2024). Intrasectoral vertical relations within public administration/government can also be part of a field of tension between different interests and obligations (e.g., the obligation to implement

national laws at the local level vs. the municipalities' obligations to respond to local conditions and needs) (Cherti et al., 2024).

Findings on the **stakeholder cooperations in the field of service provision** reveal overlaps with relevant issues of cooperations in the field of policy development, particularly with regard to funding-related relations between NGOs and the governmental sector, and the importance of horizontal relations. Most NGO/media respondents engage in horizontal (10 out of 13) and intrasectoral cooperations (10 out of 13), prevalent across local, provincial, and national levels. These cooperations often involve frequent exchanges and balanced reciprocal relations, with intrasectoral cooperations being mostly two-sided and of high or medium intensity. Considering all connections, all three stakeholder types in service provision are associated with relationships of varying intensity, focusing on horizontal and intrasectoral cooperations, as well as cooperations between public administration and NGOs/media actors. These findings align with further MIrreM research results, showing that NGOs frequently collaborate to achieve shared goals, implement projects, refer clients, and exchange data and information and that NGOs and public administration depend on each other for essential services to migrants and refugees. Project cooperation and funding create central interfaces for information exchange and collaboration, though barriers and selective exchanges also exist (Cherti et al., 2024; Hendow et al., 2024; Sloopjes, Sohst, et al., 2023).

Finally, the stakeholder network in the field of knowledge production illustrates intensive and reciprocal vertical connections across all governance levels. The emergence of these networks can probably also be attributed in part to the specific Horizon Europe Calls und fundings addressing irregular migration, irregularized migrants and regularisation.

Despite various limitations of this network analysis, we can make the following points: Social network analysis is in principle a strong tool to acquire a deeper understanding of cooperation patterns in the stakeholder field of irregular migration. Key features of network analysis allow to assess relationship characteristics, such as the frequency and reciprocity of exchanges, and to identify power asymmetries (e.g., funders vs. recipients, data owners vs. users). It also allows for analyzing homogeneity and heterogeneity by comparing actor attributes (e.g., stakeholder type and governance level), which helps reveal inclusion and exclusion mechanisms. Multiplex relationships, where multiple forms of interaction (e.g., data sharing and funding) occur simultaneously, can be visualized through network graphs, offering a deeper understanding of the complexity and dynamics of stakeholder cooperation in the field of irregular migration.

Social network analysis can make a significant contribution to an improved understanding of horizontal and vertical cooperation frameworks of different stakeholder types and related questions, such as reasons for challenges to implement measures and policies in the field of irregular migration; to what extent cooperations between stakeholders enable the provision of essential services for irregularized migrants (e.g. identification of good practice examples, the role of informal relationships or actors / institutions), which represent interfaces; or how networks (composition of actors, types of ties, etc.) are designed to support or prevent the flow of information and data.

From a methodological perspective, a key conclusion is that a qualitative, ego-centered network survey among stakeholders in the field of irregular migration—or alternatively, a multi-methods approach—would have been more promising. For instance, having research participants complete the survey prior to a more in-depth qualitative interview could have yielded more meaningful insights. This approach would have also facilitated a deeper understanding of the causal mechanisms and contextual factors influencing both vertical and horizontal cooperation among stakeholders. Furthermore, future research could benefit from whole-network analysis to capture comprehensive relational structures, improve data validity, and better understand how social ties influence decision-making, resource flows, and governance processes in the field of irregular migration.

We argue that the analysis suggests different avenues for future research. First, future studies could expand the analysis of interaction patterns to capture a more comprehensive view of stakeholder networks by incorporating whole-network approaches. This would allow for a more detailed examination of alter–alter relationships, addressing the current limitations of ego-centered data collection. Such an approach could provide a clearer picture of power asymmetries, information flows, and the intensity of cooperation across governance levels.

Second, the identification of key actors and their roles in shaping policy and data governance suggests the need to analyze how specific stakeholders influence decision-making processes. Further research could investigate how these actors' positions within the network affect agenda-setting, resource distribution, and the translation of policy into practice.

Third, the observed gaps and asymmetries in stakeholder relationships point to potential barriers to effective cooperation. Future research could examine how these gaps impact data exchange, policy implementation, and service provision. Comparative analyses across different national and local contexts would be particularly valuable in understanding how structural and institutional differences shape stakeholder interactions.

Finally, longitudinal studies could assess the stability and evolution of cooperation frameworks over time, particularly in response to changing political landscapes and funding structures. This would offer insights into the long-term sustainability of stakeholder collaborations and their ability to adapt to emerging challenges in the governance of irregular migration.

Overall, these research directions would deepen the understanding of stakeholder networks, enhance the analysis of multi-level governance, and provide evidence for improving collaborative practices in the field of irregular migration.

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7. ANNEX

7.1 MIRREM network survey

Thank you for participating in this MIRREM survey!

Your insights are valuable as we explore cooperation networks in irregular migration and regularisation policies. In this survey, we aim to understand the connections and collaborations that shape your work.

Your input will help us gain valuable insights into this important area.

Curious about MIRreM? We invite you to learn even more about the MIRreM project [here](#).

Let's dive in together—your responses will guide our understanding.

What are the top areas related to irregular migration that you work in? Select up to three.

- Border control/management and migrant smuggling
- Asylum and other protection-related policies
- Labour migration
- Return
- Detention
- Access to social services for irregular migrants
- Visa policies
- Regularisation
- Other
- I do not work at all on the topic of irregular migration.

If last option selected (I do not work at all... - should be an exclusive option in limesurvey):

Thank you for your participation. However, in this survey we are interested exclusively in the networks of actors having a stake in the area of irregular migration. You can close the browser tab now.

If more than one selected (disregard “other”):

Please rank these policy areas according to the relevance to your work.

Please choose the option that best describes the area in which you work.

- Public administration - government
- Academia, research centre or think tank
- NGO, grassroots or faith-based organisations
- Media

In which levels of governance do you operate in your work? (multiple selection possible)

- Local level
- Provincial
- National level
- Supranational level (e.g. EU)

If more than one option selected:

Please rank these levels according to relevance for your work – start with the most relevant

When it comes to irregular migrants, in which of the following areas are you involved? (multiple selection possible)

- Policy development, policy implementation and advocacy
- Service provision
- Knowledge production and knowledge transfer
- Other

If more than one option selected (disregard “other” option):

Please rank these areas according to the importance for your work – start with the most important.

We are particularly interested in the cooperation networks you make use of. By "cooperation," we refer to regular contact, data/information exchange, consultation, or direct collaboration with other stakeholders. In the following questions, we will ask you to differentiate your cooperation by the type of working area you have noted previously.

Filter: if POLICY DEVELOPMENT, POLICY IMPLEMENTATION AND ADVOCACY chosen above, else skip this part

Who do you cooperate with in the area of POLICY DEVELOPMENT, POLICY IMPLEMENTATION AND ADVOCACY?

The stakeholders you cooperate with on POLICY DEVELOPMENT, POLICY IMPLEMENTATION AND ADVOCACY are in the following levels of governance: (multiple selection possible)

- Local
- Provincial
- National
- Supranational

If more than one selected:

Please rank the partners noted above according to relevance for your work on POLICY DEVELOPMENT, POLICY IMPLEMENTATION AND ADVOCACY

Where do your cooperation partners on *POLICY DEVELOPMENT, POLICY IMPLEMENTATION AND ADVOCACY* work or belong to? (multiple selection possible)

- Public administration - government
- Academia, research centres or think tanks
- NGO, grassroots or faith-based organisations
- Media
- Other

If more than one selected (disregard “other”):

Please rank the partners noted above according to relevance for your work on *POLICY DEVELOPMENT, POLICY IMPLEMENTATION AND ADVOCACY*

How often are you in contact with cooperation partners in the area of *POLICY DEVELOPMENT, POLICY IMPLEMENTATION AND ADVOCACY*?

- More than once a week
- More than once a month
- More than once in a quarter/year
- More than once a year
- Once a year or less

In the context of *POLICY DEVELOPMENT, POLICY IMPLEMENTATION AND ADVOCACY*, please indicate the direction of collaboration and information exchange between you and your cooperation partners. Do you feel that this exchange is primarily directed from you to your partners, from them to you, or do you perceive it as being equal and mutual?

- Primarily from me to my cooperation partners
- Primarily from my cooperation partners to me
- Equal and mutual in both directions

Filter: if *SERVICE PROVISION* chosen above, else skip this part

Who do you cooperate with in the area of *SERVICE PROVISION*?

The stakeholders you cooperate with on *SERVICE PROVISION* are in the following levels of governance: (multiple selection possible)

- Local
- Provincial
- National
- Supranational

If more than one selected:

Please rank the partners noted above according to relevance for your work on *SERVICE PROVISION*

Where do your cooperation partners on *SERVICE PROVISION* work or belong to? (multiple selection possible)

- Public administration - government
- Academia, research centres or think tanks
- NGO grassroots or faith-based organisations
- Media
- Other

If more than one selected (disregard “other”):

Please rank the partners noted above according to relevance for your work on SERVICE PROVISION

How often are you in contact with cooperation partners in the area of SERVICE PROVISION?

- More than once a week
- More than once a month
- More than once in a quarter/year
- More than once a year
- Once a year or less

In the context of SERVICE PROVISION, please indicate the direction of collaboration and information exchange between you and your cooperation partners. Do you feel that this exchange is primarily directed from you to your partners, from them to you, or do you perceive it as being equal and mutual?

- Primarily from me to my cooperation partners
- Primarily from my cooperation partners to me
- Equal and mutual in both directions

Filter: if KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER chosen above, else skip this part

Who do you cooperate with in the area of KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER?

The stakeholders you cooperate with on KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER are in the following levels of governance: (multiple selection possible)

- Local
- Provincial
- National
- Supranational

If more than one selected:

Please rank the partners noted above according to relevance for your work on KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

Where do your cooperation partners on KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER work or belong to? (multiple selection possible)

- Public administration - government
- Academia, research centres, think tanks

- NGO grassroots or faith-based organisations
- Media
- Other

If more than one selected (disregard “other”):

Please rank the partners noted above according to relevance for your work on KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

How often are you in contact with cooperation partners in the area of KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER?

- More than once a week
- More than once a month
- More than once in a quarter/year
- More than once a year
- Once a year or less

In the context of KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER, please indicate the direction of collaboration and information exchange between you and your cooperation partners. Do you feel that this exchange is primarily directed from you to your partners, from them to you, or do you perceive it as being equal and mutual?

- Primarily from me to my cooperation partners
- Primarily from my cooperation partners to me
- Equal and mutual in both directions

Thank you for your participation!

Would you like to be informed about the results of this survey and sign up to the MIrreM newsletter?

I want to receive updates about the results of this survey and other MIrreM research results, through the MIrreM newsletter [please sign up here] No, thanks!/ Have already signed up.

7.2 Tables

Table 1: Respondents' Primary Areas of Work by Stakeholder Type (Percentage)

Public Administration: Policy Development: 33% Knowledge Production: 33% Service Provision: 17% Other: 17%	Academia: Knowledge Production: 62% Policy Development: 32% Service Provision: 3% Other: 3%	NGO + Media: Policy Development: 36% Service Provision: 36% Knowledge Production: 24% Other: 4%
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Table 2: Respondents' Primary Policy Areas of Interest Related To Irregular Migration by Stakeholder Type (Percentage)

Public Administration: 1. Border Control: 33% 2. Asylum: 17% 3. Labor Migration: 17% 4. Visa Policies: 11% 5. Regularization: 11% 6. Return: 6% 7. Social Services: 0% 8. Detention 0%	Academia: 1. Labor Migration: 29% 2. Border Control: 20% 3. Asylum: 18% 4. Return: 12% 5. Social Services: 12% 6. Regularization: 6% 7. Visa Policies: 3% 8. Detention 0%	NGO + Media: 1. Labor Migration: 24% 2. Asylum: 20% 3. Social Services: 20% 4. Return: 12% 5. Border Control: 8% 6. Regularization: 8% 7. Visa Policies: 4% 8. Detention 4%
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Table 3: Respondents' primary policy areas of interest related to irregular migration according to governance level in percent.

Local: 1. Asylum: 32% 2. Labour migration: 26% 3. Social services: 16% 4. Regularisation: 11% 5. Border control: 5% 6. Return: 5% 7. Visa policies: 5% 8. Detention: 0%	Provincial: 1. Labour migration: 33% 2. Social services: 33% 3. Regularisation: 17% 4. Border control: 0% 5. Asylum: 0% 6. Return: 0% 7. Visa policies: 0% 8. Detention: 0%	National: 1. Border control: 24% 2. Labour migration: 24% 3. Asylum: 16% 4. Return: 16% 5. Regularisation: 9% 6. Social services: 5% 7. Visa policies: 3% 8. Detention: 3%	Supranational: 1. Border control: 33% 2. Labour migration: 20% 3. Social services: 13% 4. Visa policies: 13% 5. Asylum: 13% 6. Return: 7% 7. Regularisation: 0% 8. Detention: 0%
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Table 4: Horizontal and vertical cooperations: primary stakeholder types (shares, %)

Public Administration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Up: 21% Down: 5% Total Vertical: 26% Horizontal: 74% 	Academia: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Up: 13% Down: 29% Total Vertical: 42% Horizontal: 58% 	NGO + Media Network: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Up: 11% Down: 17% Total Vertical: 28% Horizontal: 72%
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Table 5: Intrasectoral and intersectoral cooperations: primary stakeholder types (shares, %)

Public Administration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intrasectoral (0): 63% Intersectoral (1): 37% 	Academia Network: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intrasectoral (0): 52% Intersectoral (1): 48% 	NGO/Media Network: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intrasectoral (0): 57% Intersectoral (1): 43%
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Table 6: Contact frequency: primary stakeholder types (shares, %)

<p>Public Administration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly: 53% • Monthly: 31.5% • Quarterly: 10.5% • Less than once a year 5% 	<p>Academia:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly: 25% • Monthly: 38% • Quarterly: 21% • Yearly: 12% • Less: 4% 	<p>NGO/Media:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly: 34% • Monthly: 45% • Quarterly: 19% • Yearly: 2%
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Table 7: Cooperation direction: primary stakeholder types (shares, %)

<p>Public Administration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From me: 26% • To me: 16% • Mutual: 58% 	<p>Academia Network:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From me: 29% • To me: 8% • Mutual: 63% 	<p>NGO/Media Network:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From me: 34% • To me: 6% • Mutual: 60%
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Table 8: Horizontal and vertical cooperations: work areas (shares, %)

<p>Policy Development:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Up: 11% • Down: 17% • Total Vertical: 28% • Horizontal: 72% 	<p>Service Provision:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Up: 15% • Down: 15% • Total Vertical: 30% • Horizontal: 70% 	<p>Knowledge Production:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Up: 16% • Down: 25% • Total Vertical: 41% • Horizontal: 59%
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Table 9: Intrasectoral and intersectoral cooperations: work areas (shares, %)

<p>Policy Development:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intrasectoral (0): 53% • Intersectoral (1): 47% 	<p>Service Provision:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intrasectoral (0): 60% • Intersectoral (1): 40% 	<p>Knowledge Production:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intrasectoral (0): 57% • Intersectoral (1): 43%
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Table 10: Cooperation frequency: work areas (shares, %)

<p>Policy Development:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly: 34% • Monthly: 49% • Quarterly: 15% • Yearly: 2% 	<p>Service Provision:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly: 45% • Monthly: 35% • Quarterly: 15% • Yearly: 5% 	<p>Knowledge Production:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly: 27% • Monthly: 33% • Quarterly: 24% • Yearly: 10% • Less: 6%
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Table 11: Cooperation direction: work areas (shares, %)

<p>Policy Development:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From me to partners: 32% • From partners to me: 9% • Mutual partnership: 64% 	<p>Service Provision:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From me to partners: 30% • From partners to me: 5% • Mutual partnership: 65% 	<p>Knowledge Production:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From me to partners: 29% • From partners to me: 10% • Mutual partnership: 61%
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Table 12: Vertical and horizontal cooperations: governance level (shares, %)

Local: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Up: 21% • Down: 0% • Total Vertical: 21% • Horizontal: 79% 	Provincial: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Up: 10% • Down: 50% • Total Vertical: 60% • Horizontal: 40% 	National: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Up: 14% • Down: 17% • Total Vertical: 31% • Horizontal: 69% 	Supranational: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Up: 0% • Down: 56% • Total Vertical: 56% • Horizontal: 44%
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Table 13: Intersectoral and intrasectoral cooperations: governance level (shares, %)

Local: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intrasectoral (0): 48% • Intersectoral (1): 52% 	Provincial: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intrasectoral (0): 60% • Intersectoral (1): 40% 	National: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intrasectoral (0): 64% • Intersectoral (1): 36% 	Supranational: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intrasectoral: 37.5% • Intersectoral: 62.5%
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Table 14: Contact frequency: governance level (shares, %)

Local: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly: 55% • Monthly: 36% • Quarterly: 3% • Yearly: 6% • Less: 0% 	Provincial: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly: 20% • Monthly: 50% • Quarterly: 10% • Yearly: 20% • Less: 0% 	National: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly: 24% • Monthly: 39% • Quarterly: 29% • Yearly: 3% • Less: 5% 	Supranational: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly: 31% • Monthly: 44% • Quarterly: 19% • Yearly: 6% • Less: 0%
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Table 15: Cooperation direction: governance level (shares, %)

Local: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From Me: 39% • To Me: 0% • Mutual: 61% 	Provincial: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From Me: 10% • To Me: 10% • Mutual: 80% 	National: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From Me: 34% • To Me: 12% • Mutual: 54% 	Supranational: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From Me: 12.5% • To Me: 12.5% • Mutual: 75%
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